

Production and separation of knitted lyocell-cellulose acetate fabrics from crimped cellulose acetate fibers

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ABSTRACT

Cellulose acetate (CA) can serve as bio-favourable polyethylene terephthalate (PET) substitute in textiles, being biodegradable and mechanically disintegrable. Textile fiber production was hypothesised possible using filter tow production facilities. Different crimped CA fibers from a filter tow machine were used to produce mixed Lyocell-CA yarns via ring spinning. Yarn production, fiber-specific dyeing and subsequent material separation (recovery of 88 %) was possible by standard processes. Yarns of a 50:50 %w/w have a titer of ~46 tex (\pm g/1000 m) and a tenacity of ~0.1 N/tex. The yarns show increasing tenacity with increasing lyocell content (~0.2 N/tex for 100 % Lyocell). Furthermore, CA was separated from dispersion dye using acetone-ethanol mixtures (1:2 v/v). Though ameliorating CA fiber spinning is required for pure CA yarn production, this process is implantable on existing machinery in common machine settings. Textile CA fibers can be produced by filter tow infrastructure. CA can help reducing the atmosphere's fossil-carbon enrichment.

1. Introduction

Cellulose acetate (CA) in its commercially by far most important form cellulose diacetate with a degree of substitution (D_S) of around 2.5, has historically been relatively common in textile applications. It has been replaced by other textile fibers, of which polyethylene terephthalate (PET) is currently the most widely produced (Textile Exchange, 2021). Several factors have probably contributed to its displacement from the textile market. Due to its mechanical properties, there is a limit to the production speed. This results in higher production costs per ton of material compared to PET. Similarly, low petrol prices in recent decades enabled cost-efficient production of fossil-based fiber types. In addition, CA materials are more delicate in washing, are less resistant to detrimental chemicals and more hydrophilic compared to PET fibers. Among other reasons, and without clarifying and further elaborating on the reason, there has been a significant displacement of CA from the textile market. However, this also indicates that CA processing, finishing and applications were well known and widely used. Part of this knowledge seems hidden in old publications, partly

inaccessible by modern internet based accesses and/or language barriers, or lost due to a shift in the production orientation and textile-specific training. Any study, such as the current one, focusing on CA processing accordingly is on the peril of repeating older findings. Furthermore, the lower mechanical properties have to be considered in future industrial processes. Modern industrial machinery has to be adapted to enable CA processing, which increases production costs. It is possible that this will diminish, as machinery adaptations may lead to increased productivity in the future.

The limited chemical and microbial resistance of CA, as well as the lower mechanical properties, can also be seen as an advantage. There is a significant difference in the biodegradability of PET and CA. Although slower than the very rapidly metabolized microcrystalline cellulose powder often used as a reference material, cellulose acetate with a D_S of 2.5 has been shown to biodegrade in a variety of microbially active environments simulating natural or waste treatment conditions (Puls et al., 2011; Serbruyns et al., 2024). Cellulose acetate often exhibits a prolonged lag phase at the beginning of biodegradation tests, which is sometimes misinterpreted as a lack of biodegradability. This is due to the

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need for biofilm formation by two types of microbes, deacetylating and cellulose degrading ones. CA can undergo mechanical degradation to form microparticles. However, well-dispersed particles have a limited lifetime in various aqueous environments (Mazzotta et al., 2022; Serbruyns et al., 2024), as under soil or composting conditions (Puls et al., 2011), so there is no indication that persistent microplastics are formed. In comparison, PET, the most used textile polyester fiber (Textile Exchange, 2021), shows very low biodegradability in the natural environment (Taniguchi et al., 2019; Ward and Reddy, 2020). Consequently, it accumulates in the environment due to PET pollution (Yuan et al., 2022), partly in the form of microplastics or microfibers (Lionetto and Esposito Corcione, 2021). This is all the more serious considering that the common end-of-life of PET fabrics is incineration or land-fill (European Parliament, 2020), and that more than half of all textile fibers are PET fibers (Textile Exchange, 2021). The slow degradation of polyesters may also be partly due to the number and variety of polyester degrading microorganisms in e.g. soil (Tokawa and Calabia, 2007). The mechanical integrity of PET also hinders mechanical disintegration of products, thereby increasing the material's surface for microbial attack.

As a result, CA is estimated to be more in line with the plastic reduction targets proposed by the European Union (Publications Office of the European Union, 2022) known as the Single Use Plastic Directive (SUPD). It must be noted, that CA is not yet excluded from the SUPD. However, even if CA pollution does occur, it will be less persistent and more bioavailable. Based on the raw materials, CA is also in line with the European transition towards a bio-based and circular industry (Lange et al., 2021), which is also a goal of policy makers (European Commission, 2022, 2019). In terms of circularity, the dissolution of CA (e.g. $D_s = 2.5$ in acetone) allows for easy recycling of pure CA materials with acetone recovery. Obviously, in mixed systems, after dyeing or in post-consumer waste additional purification steps may be required. Specifically, the separation of CA and dye molecules is expected to require additional processing, as reported in PET recycling and analysis (Kato et al., 2016; Mu et al., 2023). Textile production could be an alternative to filter tow production for companies that may be affected by legislative cigarette bans (Courea and correspondent, 2024). Apart from legislation, companies are also willing to change their supply chain to non-synthetic materials, which means moving away from current processing (Trunk et al., 2022).

In order to address the processing issues of CA fibers from filter tow machines, laboratory scale CA yarn production was carried out. The formation of ring spun yarns from several different types of CA was investigated. These types were supplied as staple fibers and can easily be mixed with secondary fibers. Lyocell fibers were used to ensure overall biodegradability. Fibers were mixed, carded, pre-yarn were formed and finally ring spun. Finally, the yarns were knitted to demonstrate fabric formation. These fabrics were dyed using adequate dyeing methods for the CA and the cellulosic fraction. Finally, the separation by acetone dissolution was qualitatively assessed. A dye separation method was used to obtain a clean white CA precipitate. The aim of this study was not to address the low tensile strength of CA fibers, but to elucidate the production of CA yarn from existing filter tow machines. Accordingly, the study is more related to extending current production processes to related applications and products.

To stress the point, these crimped staple fibers were dry-spun on a commercial spinning plant for filter tow used in the manufacture of cigarette filters (Ganster and Fink, 2013). By selected settings in the production process the fiber morphology and properties are modified. This process was chosen to extend the applicability of the machine and the production capabilities without the need for infrastructure investment. Costly investment and resources in additional machinery can be avoided. It is hypothesized that such a production process is adaptable to textile fabric production (Law, 2004). The aim of the investigation is to produce textile yarns and textile structures from filter tow machine CA fibers. A range of different CA fibers were produced by varying the filter tow machinery settings. Due to the production limitation of the fiber

compression in the stuffer box, fiber mixing in the yarns suffers and yarn tenacity is expected to be reduced. Cautiously, no previous investigation or publication on filter tow fiber textiles has been found.

2. Material & methods

In order to assess the processability of the filter tow fibers, several steps were carried out to replicate an industrial process on a laboratory scale. After yarn spinning the yarns were dyed and the dyeing efficacy was investigated by dye bath extraction and color determination. To test for recycling, CA was dissolved in acetone and recovered under dye separation conditions.

2.1. Materials

6 different CA staple fibers were supplied by Cerdia Services GmbH (Freiburg, Germany) (see Appendix A: Table A1). Lyocell fibers (LyoC), which are cellulose fibers obtained from a *N*-methylmorpholine *N*-oxide (NMMO) solution dry-jet wet spinning process, with a titer of 1.7 dtex (1 decitex $\hat{=}$ g/10,000 m), were obtained from Lenzing AG (Lenzing, Austria). Acetone (> 99 %) and ethanol (> 96 %, EtOH) were supplied by Deuring GmbH & Co. KG (Hörbranz, Austria), Glauber's salt (> 99 %, Riedel de Haen, Seelze, Germany) and 25 % ammonia solution (p.a., Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG, Karlsruhe, Germany) were used. Disperse orange 62 (DO62), sold under the brand name Dianix Orange SLF (World Dye Variety, 2023), was supplied by DyStar (Singapore, Rep. of Singapore). The direct dye Solophenyl Blue 2BL 250 % (SB2), and the highly concentrated Kieralon B was from BASF (Ludwigshafen, Germany). Whatman GF/A (Little Chalfont, UK, mesh size 1.6 μ m) and Rotilabo 112A (Karlsruhe, Germany, mesh size 8–12 μ m) filters were used for CA separation. All chemicals and materials were used as received.

2.2. Yarn and fabric production

30 g of staple fibers of different fiber types were manually distributed on the conveyor belt of a laboratory card 337A (Mesdan S.p.A., Puegnago del Garda, Italy). After carding, the fleece was collected on a steel drum. A second carding run, using pure fibers or 50:50 %w/w mixtures, was carried out to obtain an initial mixture. After a third pass, the card band was drawn into the pre-yarn drawing machine. Specific attention was given to similar fleece dimensions on card entry.

The pre-yarn drawing machine Stiro Roving lab 3371 (Mesdan S.p.A.) was set to a draw ratio of 2–2.5. The machine was fed with several fractions of the card band in parallel to obtain a card band weight of (2.4 \pm 0.2) g m⁻¹. This ensures that similar fiber weights were pre-drawn. With similar feed weights, the specific fiber properties, e.g. finish and compaction, results in pre-yarn differences.

These pre-yarns were then spun on a ring spinning machine Ring Lab 3018 A (Mesdan S.p.A.). The machine was set to a draft of 25 with 800 U/m (circumvolutions per meter). This produces \sim 8 m/min of final yarn given a rotation of 6500 U/min (Rengasamy, 2010).

The yarns produced were fed into a ring knitting machine Lab Knitter 294E (Mesdan S.p.A.). The machine is equipped with 140 needles forming a ring of approx. 10 cm diameter. The machine was set to relatively soft knitting conditions to reduce stress on the yarns.

All instrument settings have been made to enable yarn spinning and knit production, not focusing of efficiency.

2.3. Yarn and fabric characterization

The textile structures produced were subjected to microscopic characterization using an Olympus SZX 16 (Tokyo, Japan) at magnifications of 0.7x, 4x, 6.3x and 8x. The mass of 10 m of yarns was used to calculate yarn fineness, a \sim 9 cm x 25 cm fabric to calculate the fabric weight. Yarn tenacity, elongation and breaking strength were

determined using a Zwick AllroundLine (Ulm, Germany) equipped with a 10 kN load cell (crosshead speed 20 mm/min).

2.4. Textile dyeing

Two different dyeing procedures were used to differentiate between only CA dyeing, as CA:LyoC dyeing (Leube, 1986). In all dyeing procedures, the actual dye content was titrated from 3 g/l dye stock solutions into the dye bath to match a 3 % shade of the textile structure. Yarn and fabric segments were approx. 0.5 g and 3 g, respectively. A spectrometric determination (350–750 nm, resolution 3 nm, halogen lamp) of the dye bath solutions was recorded to quantify the dye extraction by the sample using a Zeiss MCS601 (Oberkochen, Germany) and 1 cm polystyrene cuvettes. Fibers and fabrics were pre-treated in 25 ml/1 25 % ammonia solution with 1 g/l Kieralon B at 60 °C for 30 min (Leube, 1986).

2.4.1. CA dyeing

Approximately 0.5 g of fiber was added to approximately 25 ml of disperse dye solution in screw-capped beakers. These were held at 80 °C for 90 min before rinsing the fibers with hot and cold water. The fibers were then dried under laboratory conditions before further characterization.

2.4.2. CA:LyoC dyeing

Initial dyeing proceeded as above with addition of direct dye from stock solution and an initial temperature of 40 °C. After dye addition the temperature of the dye bath was increased to 80 °C. After 45 min, 10 % by wt. Glauber's salt was added to the dye bath. After 90 min washing was carried out as above.

2.5. Color determination

The color of dyed fibers and fabrics was determined using a colorimeter Konica Minolta CM3610d (Tokyo, Japan). Using a standard illuminant D65 at an 8° spectator angle at wavelengths of 400–740 nm with a resolution of 10 nm color values are reported with the specular component excluded. Metachromism was not considered. To eliminate the effects of fiber coiling and compressing, data are reported as the average of three subsequent sample measurements.

2.6. CA separation

First, 3 g of the dyed knit fabrics were immersed in 100 ml of acetone to dissolve the CA (Slejko et al., 2024). After extraction of the fabrics they, were again immersed in 50 ml of acetone. Finally, the fabrics were compressed and left to dry. Extensive washing was not performed. The dye eluted in acetone was spectrometrically quantified to assess the extent of dyeing and to compare it with respect to a DO62 in acetone calibration, using the Zeiss MCS601. For comparison, a cotton plain weave (GA) fabric (Getzner Textil AG, Bludenz, Austria) was included in the extraction process. Samples for extraction were dyed according to the above protocol, neglecting the pre-ammonia wash. The latter was used to estimate the influence of the fiber finish.

Finally, two-fold addition of EtOH by volume to the acetone:DO62 solution was used to separate CA and DO62. The precipitate solutions were filtered twice. First through a Rotilabo 112A filter and second through a Whatman GF/A filter. Small amounts of CA remained on the vessel walls and on the filtration unit. No further solvent was used to rinse this residues to save on chemical consumption. Precipitation of the dye from EtOH:acetone solutions was not carried out for the same reason.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Yarn and knit structures

Several CA fibers (V1-V6), of different titer and processing settings were used in the production process of the ring-spun yarn (see Appendix A: Table A1). The staple fibers were of similar fiber length to ensure their parallel application in the pre-yarn formation. Due to their inherent low tenacity, it was necessary to mix CA staple fibers with LyoC fibers. The low tenacity was unproblematic in carding and pre-yarn formation, but resulted in frequent yarn breaks in ring spinning. Accordingly, pure CA yarns could not be produced with the crimped CA fibers.

The difference in the CA fibers was based on a qualitative difference in the production machine settings. Fibers differentiate by different crimp magnitudes in the crimping chamber, as well as by the amount of coating oil, which is approx. a few percent. The crimping chamber is a prerequisite for CA web production in filter tow applications. Although it could be circumvented, it was deliberately included in this study to assess the downstream applicability of such crimped fibers. All fibers were treated with the same oil, although some fibers had a double oil application (marked +). Oil is a prerequisite in fiber and yarn spinning for lubrication, antistatic handling and plasticizing properties. The type and amount of oil directly affects the ease and possibility of fiber processing.

From the staple fibers the following yarns and knitted fabrics could be produced (Table 1). For all CA types a yarn of 50:50 (% by mass) CA:LyoC was produced. For V3, a set of yarns of mixed CA composition from 0:100 to 100:0 (% by mass) CA:LyoC, with steps of 25 % by mass, were also investigated. V3 was chosen because it has a trilobal cross-section, oil application, low crimp and an intermediate fiber titer.

Several yarns and knit fabrics could not be produced due to processing issues. The two main reasons are briefly outlined. The inherent low tenacity of the fibers is not sufficient to withstand the stresses of the spinning process. Often carding and pre-yarn formation were successful, but ring spinning was not. This low tenacity is partly due to CA, with CA ($D_s = 2.5$) having an average tenacity of 0.1–0.14 N/tex ($\hat{=} \text{N/g}/1000 \text{ m}$) (Rogowin, 1982) due to its dry-spinning conditions. The high D_s of CA hinders inter-molecular interaction, which affects tensile strength. Dry-spinning affects the mechanical intermingling and coalescence of the staple fibers. During carding, the yarns are mechanically disrupted and condensed. However this leads to disintegration, staple length reduction and yarn inhomogeneity. Eventually, the yarns are too short or inhomogeneous for the necessary fiber-to-fiber force transition. The yarn structure is stressed to the point of breakage during ring spinning. The differences in the dry spinning parameters are the reasons why version V1 and V3 did not produce knit fabrics, as the intermingling and fiber-fiber coalescence were too high.

The fiber loss in the card was determined beforehand. It was found to be less than 5 % for CA fibers and even less for LyoC fibers. Furthermore, this loss occurs during the first carding, and subsequent fiber loss is lower as the fibers are partly disentangled and pre-aligned for the second carding. It is therefore concluded that little fiber material is lost in fiber

Table 1

Properties of the produced mixed fibers, as the resulting knit fabrics. n.p. signifies that yarns, or knits, could not be produced from this staple fiber type. (n.p. not producible).

CA-type: LyoC 50:50 by wt.	Fiber titer / tex ± 10 %	Knit weight \pm g m^{-2}	V3:LyoC by wt. frac.	Fiber titer \pm tex ± 10 %	Knit weight / g m^{-2}
V1	52	n.p.	100:0	n.p.	n.p.
V2	57	205 \pm 10	75:25	40	n.p.
V3	35	n.p.			
V4	47	182 \pm 10	25:75	46	245 \pm 13
V5	39	175 \pm 9	0:100	38	194 \pm 10
V6	50	181 \pm 9			

mixtures and that the CA content in mixing ratio offsets is well below the initial 5 % of CA content. Fig 1

There are little differences in appearance for different CA fiber types. No distinct differences for the different version types can be recognized (Figure 1(a)). With increasing CA content, the yarn structure becomes more irregular (Figure 1(b)). Due to the intermingled and crimped CA fibers from dry spinning, they are not evenly distributed during carding. The propagation of force between CA bundles to adjacent fibers is hindered by this mixing issue. After ring spinning, this uneven distribution and clustering of staple fibers results in thickness variations. Such yarns suffer from uneven force distribution and are therefore weaker than well mixed CA:LyoC fibers. A lack of complete mixing of the CA and LyoC fibers results in the generation of predetermined breaking points. In addition, the CA fibers in these CA rich segments may not be perfectly aligned and only a few longitudinal fibers are load-bearing. With increasing inhomogeneities the spinning process could not be carried out. Neither softer nor slower spinning parameters were successful in fiber production.

3.2. Tensile testing of yarns

The tenacity of the yarns was determined in a tensile test. The spinning versions of CA have only a minor influence on the tenacity of the different yarns (Fig. 2a). The reported values and errors do not show significant differences between the different fiber versions. It seems that lower fiber titer and increased fiber crimp result in lower tenacity yarns. Interestingly, V3 yarns appear to have a slightly higher tenacity at a lower elongation at break (Fig. 2b). This could be due to an increased surface area compared to V6 or reduced crimp compared to V5. The lower elongation at break may be one reason why it was not compatible with the knitting process. The values obtained are comparable to the reported tenacities of commercial products of 0.1–0.12 N/tex (Pociene et al., 2004). It should be emphasized that these were produced on textile specific machinery, so the filter-tow-fiber yarns are similar in comparison.

Increasing the LyoC content results in a significant increase in tenacity (Fig. 2c,d). This is expected as the material properties of LyoC and CA suggest an increase in tenacity with increasing LyoC content. The reported tenacity of the pure LyoC yarn is lower than the reported values of 0.35–0.72 N/tex (Bechtold and Pham, 2019). Two points are noted for this difference. The current lab scale spinning process is not optimized for LyoC and reflects the process adaptations for more gentle CA spinning. Even industrially, the tenacity values of LyoC yarns are set lower to increase yarn elongation for better downstream processability.

LyoC fiber titer variation has not been investigated. It is possible that fiber titer matching could further increase the tenacity of the yarns. Low titer LyoC fibers were chosen because the yarn tenacity was superior to CA mixtures with higher titer fibers. With a lower fiber titer, more fibers per weighed portion are superior in producing a yarn, as the force transmission based on a better packing density provides more fiber-fiber contact points.

3.3. Fiber specific yarn dyeing

The yarns were dyed. Either the CA fibers only were dyed using the disperse dye DO62, or LyoC was additionally dyed using the direct dye SB2. The dyes were chosen for good optical differentiation (Fig. 3). Glauber's salt addition enhances the cellulose dye sorption by electrostatic shielding the anionic dye molecules and the slightly anionic cellulosic fabric. As disperse dyes may be salt sensitive, salt was only added after substantial dispersion dye migration into the CA fibers had occurred (Leube, 1986).

As can be seen, material selective dyeing has been achieved (Leube, 1986) (Fig. 3). Though unappealing, the mixture of yellow and blue colors allows for a clear differentiation of the fiber material. As the LyoC content increases there is a clear shift in the optical impression from yellowish/orange to blue (Fig. 3a). A similar color pattern was observed in knitted CA:LyoC fabrics (Fig. 3b). No undesirable or unexpected color pattern were observed in the knit dyeing. Staining of CA by direct dyes or LyoC fibers by dispersion dyes was optically not perceptible.

It appears that the better mixed and distributed LyoC fibers are more likely to form the fiber core, with fewer loose ends protruding into space (Fig. 3c-d). In the absence of a method for determination, this observation is qualitative. Similarly, CA fibers tend to form fiber bundles and are less regularly mixed with LyoC fibers.

During dyeing, the concentration of the dye bath can be screened to determine the level of dye exhaustion. The corresponding SB2 concentrations in the dye bath are shown in Fig. 3e. As expected, the dye concentrations in the bath decrease with increasing LyoC content in the immersed fabric. A similar trend was observed for yarn dyeing (data not shown). The dye concentration in the bath is far from exhausted. Further dye extraction could be achieved with increasing temperature as further salt addition. To note, the dyeing protocol was not optimized and the dyeing was carried out as reported (Leube, 1986).

The focus was on dissolved SB2 dye and DO62 concentrations were not assessed. Due to the disperse dye particles in the bath, the dissolved concentration changes little during the process. The disperse dye particles act as a feed to maintain the low dissolved dye concentration. As the process is far from exhaustion, a corresponding decrease of DO62 could not be observed spectrometrically. DO62 pigment size was not investigated. Obviously, with extensive water dilution or solvent exchange to e.g. acetone, changes in dye content could have been observed.

3.4. Coloration of dyed textile structures

The dyed yarns were manually compressed and their respective colors determined by the colorimeter (Fig. 4). The $L^*a^*b^*$ color space of the International Commission of Illumination is used for this purpose. The DO62 dyeing system is characterised by relatively light colours ($L^* > 60$) with increasing b^* values (Fig. 4a). The b^* -values represent the increasing yellow tint of the samples, accompanied by a small change in a^* .

More pronounced changes in L^* and b^* values occur in the DO62-SB2

Fig. 1. Fiber structures after spinning of (a)50:50 by weight mixtures of the different CA fibers with LyoC and (b) different V3:LyoC mixing ratios. All yarns are dyed using DO62.

Fig. 2. Obtained yarn tenacities for (a) 50:50 CA:LyoC yarns of the different CA staple fibers at (b) its respective breaking elongation. (c) Force evolution of V3-CA: LyoC mixtures of different composition in tensile testing until yarn fracture which resulted in (d) different CA:LyoC composition yarn tenacities. Error bars in (a)+(b)+(d) and (c) shaded areas derive from standard deviation of multiple measurements. Coloration of (c + d) is in respective sample colors after dyeing according to method 2.4.

dyeing. The prominent b^* -change represents the blue coloration with increasing LyoC content (Fig. 4c). As the blue color intensifies, the corresponding L^* also decreases towards darker shades. Besides, the color strength of the blue fraction of the mixed dyed fabrics is superior to that of the yellow fraction.

Between different fiber types of knit fabrics the color strength $K S^{-1}$ ($\hat{=}$ absorption (K) to scattering (S) coefficient) differences are small (Fig. 4b). However, V4 fibers have less oil on the fibers, which is related to the higher color strength in the dyed knit fabric. In addition, V5 has a higher crimp index which appears to result in more inhomogeneous yarns. Due to the higher CA fiber bundles, the sample appears more blue overall, resulting in a peak in the $K S^{-1}$ spectra similar to the samples with decreasing CA content (Fig. 4c).

Several influences can affect the $K S^{-1}$ differences. Disperse dye molecules must dissolve before being embedded in CA. Due to the limited solubility of the dye, this process may be slow and the color strength of the fabric may suffer from dye uptake. In addition, having different molecular weights the absolute concentration of the dye molecules in the dye bath, at equal mass concentration, might differ. Also, the dyeing rate of CA of $D_s=2.5$ is reduced compared to less acetylated cellulose (LaNieve, 2007). Finally, the mass to surface area ratio changes with decreasing staple fiber titer. The finer LyoC fibers have a higher surface to mass ratio. Relatedly, the more dye molecules absorbed by the fiber the higher the $K S^{-1}$ value. For dyeing an equal color strength the mass concentration of SB2 dye in the dye bath could be reduced or that of DO62 increased. Alternatively, the dyeing procedure could be modified to prolong the CA dyeing prior to the addition of Glauber's salt, or to start at a higher temperature to increase CA dye uptake (LaNieve, 2007).

3.5. Dye-separation CA recycling

Finally, the dyed fabrics were immersed in acetone to dissolve the CA component. The dissolution of CA, given a D_s of 2.5, is rapid at laboratory temperature and is achieved within minutes (Fig. 5a).

As the CA content in the mixed yarns increases, an increasing amount of DO62 is dissolved in the acetone solution. This corresponds to an

increased yellow optical perception. The amount of dye dissolved out can be quantified with the use of a DO62:acetone calibration using spectrometry (Fig. 5c).

However, the data is quite scattered for different versions of CA. This probably corresponds to the fiber properties. V2 has a higher fiber titer. During dyeing, these fibers absorb less dye due to a lower surface/mass ratio. Accordingly, less dye is eluted during CA recovery.

This may also result from the yarn structure. Due to CA inhomogeneities in the yarns, there might be compositional inhomogeneities in the fabric. Due to different dye affinities, samples with lower CA content result in lower DO62 elution in acetone upon dissolution. Therefore, the quantification obtained is a qualitative estimate. The amount of dye molecules eluted is indicative of the amount of dye incorporated in the dyeing process, neglecting systematic loss or dye retention.

It is interesting to note that even from fabrics without CA (0–100 and GA) a small amount of DO62 can be quantified. It is assumed to come from partition of disperse dye in LyoC and cotton fabrics. The dye partition is a many times higher in knit fabrics than in compact woven structures.

After addition of EtOH the precipitated CA settles to the bottom of the flasks (Fig. 5b). Apart from minor color shading, the filter residue is optically white after drying as expected (see Supplementary Info S1). However, minor DO62 and SB2 partition is present, especially with LyoC yarn residues from the fabric cutting. The filtration residue can be compared to the weight loss of acetone immersed fabrics. For simplicity we assume this residue to be only/mainly CA. (88 ± 1) % of the CA can be recovered in this simple two-step recycling process (see Appendix A: Table A2). Thus, most of the dissolved CA can be recovered by precipitation. Efficacy will increase with process size and process maturity.

In addition, using the weight share of CA in the fabric, the extraction efficiency of CA dissolution can be qualitatively assessed (see Appendix A: Table A2). This is based on the assumption that the CA content of the knit fabric correlates with the weight mixtures in the card and that mixing flaws are neglected. Obviously, less CA is dissolved than would be expected, meaning that some CA remains in the knit fabric structure. We found CA impurities after acetone extraction under the microscope

Fig. 3. Optical representation of (a) mixed dye yarns with alternation in the CA:LyoC weight composition, (b) a dyed 50:50 %w/w mixed yarn knit fabric of V4-CA. Microscopic images of single yarns reveal the present fiber type by specific coloration in (c) a DO62 dyed 50:50 % w/w mixed yarn of V4-CA and (d) a DO62 and SB2 dyed 50:50 %w/w mixed yarn of V3-CA. (e) Dye bath concentration of direct dye SB2 after 1.5 h of 0.5 g mixed fiber knit fabric in 25 ml dye fluid from solution spectrometry.

(see Supplementary Info S2). Although the extraction rates are high, they could be improved, e.g. with additional extraction steps. Only the 25:75 sample shows higher CA dissolution than expected. It is assumed that this is due to LyoC yarn and fiber fragments washing off. A similar effect was observed in 0:100 fabrics, where small amounts of dyed LyoC fibers were found on the filter. As these were related to weight loss on acetone extraction, the proportions reported are high, corresponding to little material.

In summary, there is almost complete dissolution of CA from the knit fabrics in acetone, of which we lose minor amounts through precipitation and separation in recycling.

Several losses occur during the CA recovery process that reduce the amount of recovered CA. Primarily it is process losses. CA condensates remain on vessel walls as the filtration unit used. It can only be partly rinsed or scraped off, as solvent options are limited. Alcohols do not enable rinsing and CA solvents cannot be used. In addition, minor amounts of CA in the acetone present in the LyoC knits after acetone extraction remain. As a result, precipitation efficacy can also be improved.

As EtOH is added, the mixtures cool and precipitation is slow. After a while, small precipitates appear and grow for hours and days. The solution mixtures were left for >7 days at lab temperature (~ 23 °C) to allow for equilibrium precipitation. However, it cannot be excluded that small amounts of CA were still dissolved, when passing through the filter. Optically, there were no particles in the filtrate. Accordingly, the pore size of the filter chosen was adequate.

The choice of EtOH for precipitation came from the consideration of the separation of CA and DO62. Obviously CA could also be precipitated in water, but DO62 would migrate into the precipitate. With the EtOH blend, the solubilities of DO62 and CA diverge. Possibly the dye could be precipitated in an additional separation step, e.g. using a tertiary component, or accelerated by increasing the temperature. Comparable approaches work with multi-component mixtures for fiber density reduction and dye separation, where elevated temperatures and multiple cycles are required (Mu and Yang, 2022). A similar multi-step approach using benzyl alcohol was successful (Mu et al., 2023). In conclusion, simple dye-CA separation in acetone:EtOH solvents is possible given the precipitation time.

4. Critical assessment of the investigation

The yarn production process has been carried out on laboratory devices. With further process adjustments more homogenous yarns could be produced. Additionally, further improvements in CA staple dry spinning may improve downstream processability. This may include adjustments to the production machine, such as intermediate drying loops. A comprehensive evaluation of yarn homogeneity could be carried out to better understand why some yarns are suitable for knitting and others aren't.

The knitting process was adjusted to be gentle. On a laboratory scale, slower and less efficient processes are of little concern, but may hinder the adaptation of such processes on an industrial scale. Further process

Fig. 4. Color specification using (a) L^* , a^* , b^* values of only DO62 dyed yarns by V3-CA content (0 %: 100(DO62), 25 %: 25 (DO62), 75 %: 75 (DO62)) as different CA-version (50 % CA of V1-V6) and of mixed dye system DO62:SB2 for alternating V3-CA:LyoC compositions (0 % V3: 100, 25 % V3: 25, 50 % V3: 50, 75 % V3: 75). Spectral color strength $K S^{-1}$ of (b) knit fabrics 50:50 wt% of different CA version and (c) of mixed-dyed yarns in the visible region for different V3-CA:LyoC compositions (75 % CA: solid, 50 % CA: dotted, 25 % CA: dashed and 0 % CA: dot-dashed). Markers and lines are in the respective colors of the samples (with exception to Fig 4b).

adaptation, investigation and experimentation is required for acceptable industrial application.

The yarns are in a random coiled state under the spectrometer for color determination. To ensure comparability and less variation in $L^*a^*b^*$ -values, the yarn surfaces should be uniform.

The separation mixture of CA and DO62 was chosen for reasons of simplicity and toxicity. Other solvent or component systems might be advantageous (Kato et al., 2016). Especially considering the subsequent solvent separation or the limited solubility of the precipitating components. Besides, further purification of the precipitated CA might be required.

5. Conclusion

Several CA staple fibers have been produced by a non-textile specific process, dry spinning including a stuffer box. Fibers were produced on an industrial scale filter tow machine at selected settings. There appears to be only minor differences between the different CA staple fibers, apart from minor coloration and tenacity differences. As fiber titer increases, tenacity appears to increase and dye bath extraction decreases. Increased crimp results in increased dyeing of the fibers. From CA:LyoC yarns knit fabrics were produced without severe limitations. Therefore, the research hypothesis is confirmed and crimped fibers from filter tow machines can be used in textile applications. However, it seems that fine (< 3 dtex) secondary staple fibers, in the case of LyoC, are essential in mixed fibers in this process. Selective dissolution of CA in acetone, including separation of dispersion dyes from CA by selective CA-ethanol precipitation, was carried out as a recycling option. Overall, the separation efficacy in the simple laboratory experiment is close to 90 %.

Given the low toxicity, cost and good recoverability of acetone, the recycling process could be relevant in industrial applications where acetone recovery is close to 99 %.

In the future better mixing of CA fibers, based on less fiber coalescence and intermingling from the production process, is expected to result in stronger yarns. Future improvements in staple fiber properties will make downstream processes simple, possibly faster and more cost-effective. Fiber titer matching and spin finishes are options for further comprehensive yarn adaptation.

The problems in the processing and application of CA have to be counter-balanced by follow-up properties and costs. Due to its predominantly amorphous structure with low interpolymer forces and correspondingly low mechanical strength, it is more susceptible to mechanical disintegration in the environment. As the size of the material decreases, the available surface for microbial attack increases. Compared to PET, CA is much less persistent in the environment, does not or to a lesser extent enviro-accumulate, and helps to reduce fossil-based carbon enrichment of the atmosphere. This is without taking into account the energy used in the production process, which is being shifted to renewable sources globally. Consequently, despite its performance drawbacks, CA may be the more reasonable choice of material in textile applications. Especially when considering the true costs, including unquantifiable environmental costs of current fiber market shares.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Florian Wurm: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Florence Schöb:** Methodology,

Fig. 5. (a) Acetone dissolution of knitted mixed fabrics of different CA fibers in the two-stage extraction process (first step in the back: 100 ml acetone, second step in the front: 50 ml acetone), (b) settled CA precipitate after addition of EtOH with the dye in solution and (c) solution spectrometric signal of DO62 after dissolving CA of 3 g knitted CA:Lyoc fabrics in 100 ml acetone (first extraction step) respectively (GA – plain weave cotton fabric).

Investigation. **Tina Moor:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation. **Julia Schweiß:** Resources. **Jörg Leukel:** . **Tung Pham:** Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Thomas Bechtold:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

J. Schweiß and J. Leukel work for Cerdia International Services GmbH, which produce and sell cellulose acetate. This is clear from the affiliation (title page) however.

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Supplementary materials

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Appendix A

Properties of the different used CA fibers are listed in [Table A1](#). All fibers were produced with the same oil.

Appendix A

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the revision of this work the corresponding author used [deepl.com/write](https://www.deepl.com/write) in order to correct grammar and language errors. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Table A1

Properties of the CA staple fibers of 35 mm length, as of LyoC staple fibers of 34 mm length. Crimp index (more(+)) and less(-)) and spin oil (single(-) and double(+)) application) are listed as qualitative measures.

Material	Descriptor	Cross-section	Titer (dtex)	Crimp index	Spin oil
CA	V1	Trilobal	1,67	–	+
	V2	Trilobal	5,56	–	+
	V3	Trilobal	3,33	–	+
	V4	Trilobal	3,33	–	–
	V5	Trilobal	3,33	+	+
	V6	Cloud-shaped	3,33	–	+
LyoC	Tencel	Round	1,3		

Specific sample recuperation share per CA version is listed in Table A2. No clear differences in recuperation efficacy were found, though minor changes exist.

Table A2

Proportion of CA recuperated from alcoholic precipitation after acetone extraction of CA:LyoC knit fabrics.

Sample	CA version	CA dissolved /%	CA recuperation /%
0:100		0	59 ± 21
25:75	V3	103	88.3 ± 0.5
50:50	V2	93	89.0 ± 0.3
	V4	95	85.8 ± 0.2
	V5	97	89.7 ± 0.6
	V6	95	87.6 ± 0.5

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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